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Empirical study of customer retention strategies of small retail shoppers.

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Key words

Customer retention, organized retailing, FDI, CRM, Likert scale, regression

Abstract

Indian retailing is one of the largest fragmented and the least organized industries. The knocks of the organized retailers have posed threats to the existence of unorganized small retail shoppers. A study with its objective to explore the adopted promotional strategies, customer retention measures and patronizing shop strategies has been carried out. The results of the study have been analyzed using a survey data of 200 small retail shoppers they have been selected through convenient sampling and reveal that sales of small shoppers are declining. 78 and 67 percent of grocery and apparel shoppers respectively offer credit facility to their customers. 98 and 67 percent of grocery and apparel shoppers respectively offer credit facility to their customers. 98 percent small shoppers have attracted customers by offering better quality goods. Information obtained from a sample of 200 customer visitors of the sampled retail shop reveals that 78 percent customers have patronized the grocery shops because of credit facility and 82 percent due to better quality and home delivery. In case of Bakery, some 90 percent customers patronize the shop because of quality products. The study also reveals that the personal behaviour of small retail shoppers play a vital role to retain customers. Retailers use flexibility in terms of Customer Retention Strategies and modify them with changing circumstances and conditions of organized retailers so as to meet the challenges of the competitive environment.

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